

FORT OF RAISEN

By

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Situated at 23°-20'N and 77°-7'E, 29 miles from Bhopal, the fort of Raisen stands on a sandstone spur of the Vindhya, 1980 feet above the sea level. Nothing is known of the foundation of the fort which is said to have been built during early Hindu rule in Malwa. Probably its name appears to be a corruption of Rajavasini or the royal residence, but might possibly be derived, according to a local tradition, from the name of its founder Rai Singh.¹

Description

The fort is surrounded by a massive wall of stone masonry having nine gateways, eight large and one small. Of these three gates are on its north, three on its west and two on its south, but the wicket is on the western side. A huge stone fixed on the third gate in the north is carved with a lion in the centre and two *sawars* riding on a horse and an elephant attacking the lion with spears. According to a local belief it is inferred to be a code sign for a hidden treasure.

The wall is surmounted by thirteen bastions, three on the east, five on the north and three on the west. Each bastion has the capacity of accommodating three machine guns. The fort has an area of 480 sq. Bigha excluding the buildings. The circumference of the fort is between 2½ and 3 miles and its shape is oblong. There are remains of numerous buildings inside the fort. Nawab Sikandar Begam, the ruler of Bhopal, mentioned in her 'tour volume' sixty-five buildings inside, of which twenty-five are in ruins and forty standing.

Madrasa and Mosque

There is a large and well-built college, known as *Madrasa* with a capacity of accommodating 400 students. To the *Madrasa* (College) is attached a fine mosque wherein more than a hundred persons can offer prayers. It is 19 yards long and 8 yards broad with five doors and six pillars. In the courtyard of the mosque is a water reservoir, the central arch of which is inscribed in Arabic letters with a Persian verse indicating that the *Madrasa* and the mosque were built by Nawab Ghanimul-mulk in 890 A. H. A local tradition calls it *Baradari Alamgiri* which is not correct as is clear from the following Persian couplets inscribed there:

1. Indian Antiquary, XIX, p. 352

'Ahad-i-Sultan-us-Saiatīn Shah Sultan-i-Ghias

Shah Jahangīr ast sarwar-i-taj-i- shāhān-i-Shah ast

Rakht īn khursand Masjid gumbad-i-dāro madār

Milk Razi īn ast Chhajju maqta-i-nāmdar

Ghānimul-Mulk mukhātab shudaz hazrat-i-shahinshah

Nām khud dar mulk kard az Qudrat Ullah

Sabūn sitta tisin wa saman maya murattab shud

Wahidul Qayyum Hayyul he lam-ulid wa huwal-Hakim

Malik Razi Chajju who was conferred a title of Ghanimul-mulk constructed the building consisting of a *Madrasa* and *masjid* in 890 A.H. in the reign of Sultan Ghiyasuddin of Malwa. The last couplet, however, indicates that the construction of the building was begun in 890 A. H. and completed in 897 A. H.

Tomb

Adjoining the mosque to its south stands a tomb known as *Pir Silahuddin Ka Mazar*. Nothing is known about the saint whose history is still shrouded in mystery. Raisen, however, had been a stronghold of the Rajputs of Malwa and had played an important role in the history of central India, owing to its unique position. The scanty records throwing light on Raisen reveal that one Silahuddin was a Rajput convert to Islam and had been a famous Hindu chieftain possessing a large territory and army.

When Bahadur Shah of Gujarat conquered the fort of Raisen in 1532, Silhadi, a Purbiya Rajput, professed Islam in the name of Silahuddin and was slain with other Rajputs there. Moreover Silhadi (Silahuddin) also joined in 1527 the forces of Rana Sanga with an army of 30,000 horses at Khanwa, the crucial and the famous battle which was fought between Babur and the Indian chiefs under Rana Sanga.

Thus the tomb known as *Pir Silahuddin Ka Mazar* may be presumed to be the eternal resting place of the great warrior Silhadi (Silahuddin) who not only held the districts of Raisen, Bhilsa and Sarangpur under his sway but also played an important role in the history of Malwa during the sixteenth century.

Another mosque known as "masjid Sher Shah" was built in 951 A. H. It is 26 yds. long and 12 yds. broad. The boundary wall is strong and high, but the mosque is ruined and has lost its dome. There are three tunnels to its left side; one of them leads to Sita Talai, a tank situated outside the fort.

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palaces in this fort. There are some palaces of Hindu times namely Atardar ka Mahal, Badal Mahal, Raja Rohini Ka Mahal and Hawa Mahal, which constitute remains of magnificent palaces in this fort.

(a) *Atardar Ka Mahal* is an elegant structure with ten doors and hundreds of *takchas*. It is 8 yards long and 5 yards broad and has an underground storey.

(b) *Badal Mahal and Raja Rohini Ka Mahal* are two-to three-storeyed ruined palaces, attesting the building skill of the age. There are several Hindi inscriptions on the wall and some rock-paintings representing hunting scenes.

(c) *Hawa Mahal*. A splendid specimen of palace architecture, it is a three-storeyed structure with tall pillars numbering 70 to 80. The verandah of the first floor has lost its ceiling and doors. Below it are underground cells meant for the accommodation of the sepoy for the safety of the fort in times of emergency.

The fort has four famous water reservoirs known as Dura, Duri, Madagan and Sagar and forty-eight *tanks* (wells).

Inscriptions

There are inscriptions in Hindi and Persian on the walls and on the eastern gate of the fort.

(1) *Inscription in Hindi*

“१५८२ विक्रमाजीत माघ वदी अठमी सोम राम नाम सलहदू महाराज . . .”

(2) *Inscription in Persian*

..... Dar 'amal Aurangzeb 'Alamgīr Badshah Ghāzi ba ihtimām Khwaja Yaqūt Haris wa Sheikh Bahauddīn wa Muhammad Amīn wa Haji Muhammad Ashraf wa Anoop Rai Tahvīldar dar hukumat Muhammad Mansūr..... Az tarikh Yakum shahr Rabi-us-sani 35 A. H. Lighayat nauzdahum Shabān 38 A. H. murattab shud-Ganga Ram Maimār-1106 A. H.

The repairs of the buildings and ramparts of the fort of Raisen were executed in the reign of Emperor Aurangzeb Ghazi under the supervision of Khwajah Yakut Haras, Sheikh Bahauddin, Muhammad Amin, Haji Muhammad Ashraf and Anup Rai Tahsildar under the governorship of Mansur and Muhammad Abid Khan Diwan being his deputy, between the first of Rabi-us-sani of the 35th year of the reign and the 19th Shaban of the 38th year.

History

Malwa had been ruled for two centuries and a half by the Paramara chiefs whose capital was at first Ujjain and later Dhar. The line was distinguished for patronage of learning and in this respect Bhoja was the most celebrated prince of this house. By the beginning of the 13th century the Paramaras were ousted by the Tomars. Malwa, being

a highway between the northern and southern provinces, remained a bone of contention between the Hindu and Muslim kings and in 1234, Sultan Iltutmish invaded Malwa and sacked Bhilsa and Ujjain and captured the forts of Bhilsa and Mandu. It is probable that Raisen shared the fate of Bhilsa in 1235¹. According to a chronicler he conquered the fort of Raisen in 622 A. H. along with adjoining territories including Bhilsa and Ashta.² In 1292 A. D. Alauddin Khilji led an expedition into Malwa and captured the stronghold of Bhilsa.³ The fort of Raisen was also taken by him in 692 A. H. —1293 A. D. Muhammad-bin-Tughlaq captured the fort of Raisen and Bhilsa and merged Raisen in Saugor Province.⁴

In the fifteenth century it was regarded as one of the strongholds of the Sultans of Malwa. Nasiruddin of Malwa had employed in his army a large number of Rajputs from eastern Hindustan who became so powerful in the kingdom that Mahmud II was reduced to the position of puppet in their hands. Medni Rai had established himself in the northern and eastern districts of the kingdom, his officers held Chanderi and Gagron and his brother Silhadi, Raisen, Bhilsa and Sarangpur. When Bahadur Shah of Gujarat annexed Malwa in 1531, he made over Ujjain, Ashta and Bhilsa to Silhadi in Jagir. After some time Bahadur Shah became suspicious and determined to attack him on the plea that he had enslaved many Muslim women and introduced them into his harem. Bhopat, his son, was at this time in Bahadur Shah's court. He lost no time to warn his father about the evil designs of Bahadur Shah, who proceeded to parcel out Malwa and put Habib Khan into Ashta, Dana Khan into Ujjain and Mallu Khan into Sarangpur. In 1532 Bahadur Shah captured Bhilsa which Silhadi had held for 18 years and then proceeded to Raisen. The town of Raisen and the fort were at that time in the hands of Lakshman Singh, Silhadi's brother, who was defeated by Bahadur Shah and retired into the fort. After the siege had lasted for some days, Silhadi, being quite sure that it must fall and his wife and family who were living there, would probably be killed, offered to become a musalman in the name of Salahuddin, if the garrison were spared and to arrange for surrender of the fort. Lakshman knowing that Bhopat was bringing Rana Sanga for help, did not agree to Silhadi's suggestion. Silhadi was eventually imprisoned in the fort of Mandu. Lakshman seeing that Rana's efforts proved futile, agreed to surrender the fort on the release of his brother. Bahadur Shah acceded to his request and Silhadi was pardoned but when Silhadi having been recalled from Mandu, was again permitted to enter Raisen, he was

1. *Central India State Gazetteer Series*, Vol. II, p. 112

2. *Dafter Gazetteer (compiled 133 A. H.) Tarikh-1- Raisen*, by Sahshwani.

3. *Ibid.* 4. *Ibid.*

persuaded to perform the rite of *jauhar* rather than incur the disgrace of being implicated in the surrender. Meanwhile Durgavati, Silhadi's wife, the daughter of Rana, committed *jauhar* with some 700 women in the fort. The Rajputs with their garments dyed yellow according to custom, rushed desperately from the fort and all were slain. Thus the fort of Raisen fell on May 10th 1532, into the hands of Bahadur Shah who then put Bhilsa, Chanderi and Malwa under the governorship of Sultan Alam Khan Lodi, a son of Bahlol Lodi.

Humayun, the Mughal Emperor, who was to attend to his eastern possessions where Afghan intrigue was most dangerous at that time displayed better qualities of determination against Bahadur Shah. He directed his brothers Hindal and Askari who were at Agra to attack the invaders and himself moved through eastern Malwa to Sarangpur receiving the capitulation of the strong fortress of Raisen on the way and handed it over to Qawan Khan, *Amil* of Bhilsa. After the defeat of Bahadur Shah by Humayun at Mandu (1535), Mallu Khan of Sarangpur managed to annex most of Central and Eastern Malwa and proclaimed himself king under Kadir Shah. Bhopat Rai who held Raisen at this time paid tribute to him and acknowledged his supremacy. It was short-lived and in 1542 Sher Shah entered Malwa and ousted Kadir Shah from his possessions, and placed an Afghan Governor with the title of Shujaat Khan in charge. His next move was against the Rajputs of Raisen who had become prominent first under Medni Rai and under Silhadi who had assisted Rana Sanga at Khanua in 1527 A. D. At this time Raisen and Chanderi were held by Puran Mal who was holding the estate for Partab Rai, the infant son of Bhopat Rai. On reaching Gagron, Shujaat Khan, the viceroy of Malwa sent Ram Shah the Tomar Raja of Gwalior to bring Puran Mal, who however refused to come along with him until Shujaat Khan himself went. Puran Mal's wife suspected treachery and spoke to Shujaat Khan when Puran Mal was going: "I will then break my fast when I shall see Puran Mal again and the whole time he is away, I will sit on a bastion of the fort and watch his return". The power of the Rajput chief may be guessed from the fact that Puran Mal entered the presence of Sher Shah with a retinue of 6000 young horsemen. He was well received and returned in safety leaving his brother Chhattar Mal as hostage.

Puran Mal had shortly after occupying the town of Chanderi massacred most of its inhabitants and collected in his harem 2000 women, Muslim as well as Hindu. In 1543 Sher Shah marched from Agra against him and besieged the fort. This expedition of Sher Shah according to Abbas Khan had been provoked by the oppression of Musalman families by Raja Puran Mal. But Prof. Qanungo definitely says "It was not undertaken out of religious motive to punish Puran

Mal for enslaving the families of the Muslims of Chanderi as the bigoted historians fondly believed....". No incentive of fanaticism was necessary as the political object was a sufficient stimulant to move Sher Shah against Raisen. One single fort unsubdued might overturn an empire, as Sher Shah could realise by contemplating the fate of Humayun. So he determined to safeguard himself against unknown dangers by rooting out Rajput influence in Malwa. Whatever might have been the motive or incentive for the attack, Puran Mal and his companions as Abbas Khan says "like hogs at bay failed not to show their valour and gallantry; but all were slain in the twinkling of an eye," in spite of the terms offered by Sher Shah. In any case it was a disgraceful episode in Sher Shah's generally honourable career. Sher Shah made over the fort of Raisen to Munshi Shahbaz Khan Sarwani and made it one of his principal forts manning it with a large garrison including 1000 artillery.

When Humayun recovered his throne in 1555 A.D., Shujaat Khan abstained from acknowledging him and regarded himself in all respects as an independent sovereign. Later in the same year he died and was succeeded by his son Baz Bahadur who was defeated by the officers of Akbar in 1561. Thus Malwa including the fort of Raisen which was then under Malik Mustafa, his own younger brother, became a province of Mughal empire.

In the reign of Akbar, Raisen was regarded as the headquarters of a sarkar in the Subah of Ujjain. Aurangzeb, the Mughal Emperor was not only attracted by the strategic position of the fort but made certain additions in the original construction and till today, they are visible to the eyes of the research scholars of history.

Faiz Muhammad of Bhopal besieged the fort of Raisen about 1760 A.D. and the imperial Governor Nuid Ali Khan Khwajasera was killed. Somewhat alarmed at the possible results of this attack on an imperial official, the Nawab wrote to Delhi explaining that he suspected the Governor of wishing to become independent and had taken this step to prevent it. In reply he was thanked and a title Faizuddoulah Faiz Muhammad Khan Bahadur Fateh Jang was conferred on him and a farman making over the fort formally to the Nawab of Bhopal from Alamgir II Mughal Emperor *alias* Shah Alam II was also granted to him. In 1796 Raisen passed in the hands of Bala Rao *Ingli*, but was soon recaptured by Wazir Muhammad in 1798 and has since then remained in the possession of the royal families of Bhopal, till Nawab Muhammad Hamidullah Khan, the last ruler of Bhopal State, handed it over to the Government of India in 1949 when his State was merged in the Indian Union.

General

Raisen is reckoned among the most renowned forts of Malwa and has played an important role in the History of Malwa from its foundation in Hindu times, but it is hardly mentioned by historians before the 15th century. Abul Fazl remarks that it is one of the famous forts of Hindustan. It occupied the constant attention of various Muslim paramount powers in different times by virtue of its unique position which always exerted a strong influence on events in this part of India.

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